

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS AND INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article examines the significance of digital technologies and interactive methods in teaching foreign languages. Today, the role of digital technologies is extremely important in engaging young people in education and enhancing the learning process. In particular, modern interactive methods and digital platforms used in foreign language learning, such as mobile applications, online courses, virtual learning environments, and useful platforms, create new opportunities for both teachers and students. Additionally, digitized education tailored to foreign language learning contributes to the development of cultural exchange and global communication.

Keywords: educational technologies, digitalization, interactive, platforms, online education, virtual environment, cultural exchange.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalarning va interaktiv metodlarning qanchalik ahamiyatga egaligi ko'rib chiqiladi. Hozirgi kunda yoshlarni ta'limga jalb qilish va ta'lim jarayonini yanada yoritish uchun raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni juda katta. Ayniqsa, xorijiy tillarni o'rganishdazamonaviy interaktiv metodlarning va raqamlashgan platformalarning, masalan, mobil ilovalar, onlayn kurslar, virtual dars muhitlari va foydali platformalar, ustozlarga va talabalarga yangidan yangi imkoniyatlar yaratib beradi. Shuningdek, xorijiy tillarni o'rganishga moslashtirilgan raqamlashgan ta'lim madaniyatlar almashanuvini va global kommunikatsiyasini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim texnologiyalari, raqamlashtirish, interaktiv, platformalar, onlayn ta'lim, virtual muhit, madaniy almashinuvlar.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается значение цифровых технологий и интерактивных методов в преподавании иностранных языков. Сегодня цифровые технологии играют важную роль в привлечении молодежи к образованию и в повышении увлекательности учебного процесса. В частности, современные интерактивные методы и цифровые платформы для изучения иностранных языков, такие как мобильные приложения, онлайн-курсы, виртуальные учебные среды и полезные платформы, открывают новые возможности как для преподавателей, так и для студентов. Кроме того, цифровое образование, адаптированное к изучению иностранных языков, способствует культурному обмену и глобальной коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: образовательные технологии, цифровизация, интерактивные платформы, онлайн-образование, виртуальная среда, культурный обмен

In modern education directions, digital technologies, in particular artificial intelligence (AI), play an important role and also have strategic priorities. Due to the rapid development of technologies, the educational process is being fundamentally updated, and the transition from old teaching methods to new digital and innovative methods is accelerating. Of course, the system of teaching foreign languages is no exception. Currently, the use of artificial

intelligence is considered not only a requirement of the time, but also the foundation of quality education.

Smart learning platforms exist not only in higher education but also in general secondary education. Digitized platforms, for example, “Kundalik.com,” are smart platforms that electronically provide parents with information about students’ achievements and shortcomings in lessons. A wide range of opportunities has also been created for higher education students, and currently they are making very effective use of these opportunities. As Giyasova A. [1] mentions that “Digital technologies, particularly mobile apps, online courses, and interactive platforms, make the language learning process engaging for students and tailored to their needs. Moreover, these technologies enable teachers to monitor the quality of education and organize students' learning process more effectively. The article highlights digitized methods in foreign language learning, their place and importance in the educational system, as well as their role in enhancing the effectiveness of this process”. This observation shows that students nowadays have a data portal and opportunity to useful technologies.

Individual approach. Digital technologies such as **Chatbots, Duolingo, and Lingvist** help students to improve their speaking skills. Students can customize these platforms and use them anywhere very conveniently. This platform enables them to save time and receive instant feedback, and it is one of the strengths of the education system. In the automated system, students can immediately see their mistakes and correct them by consulting with artificial intelligence. As Raxmonov I. [2] mentioned that “Digital platforms, however, allow these limitations to be overcome, present learning materials using multimedia tools, assess students' knowledge in real time, and shape individualized learning trajectories.”

In conclusion, modern education shows that artificial intelligence is effective, particularly in its didactic potential for teaching foreign languages.

They make a significant contribution to individualizing education, allowing students to use platforms according to their preferences, providing learning materials, and enhancing the efficiency of the learning process. It is an artificial intelligence that helps develop independent learning skills, provides prompt and accurate feedback, and assists in creating the educational process in an engaging and effective way.

At the same time, by combining traditional methods with new technologies, there is a shared desire to create a highly effective education system and to provide higher education for everyone. In the future, one of the key tasks will be the widespread implementation of artificial intelligence technologies in the education system, their methodological improvement, and the development of teachers' digital competencies.

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